

ISic1632

I.Sicily inscription 1632

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

mosaic

Object

mosaic

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Halicyae

Place of origin (modern)

Salemi

Provenance

Central panel of mosaic/basilica B, in the paleo-Christian basilica first excavated by Salinas in 1893

Coordinates

37.833019, 12.808066

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Salemi

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

tessillis

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: not recorded mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not recorded mm

Text

1. Κοβουλδέους κ[ἐ] Μα
2. [ξ]ίμα ξύχην [έ]πλή
3. [ρ]ωσαν ύπερ [σ]ω
4. [τ]ηρία[ς] αύτων κέ [τ]έκν(ων)

Apparatus

Text of Bilotta via SEG 36.828

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645083

EDR 108400

PHI 331388

Bibliography

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undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

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Troina. At 307 H11-12 fig.92

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